

DEVELOPING STUDENT-CENTERED TEACHING AND LEARNING AT SCHOOL

Damirova Gulshoda Utkir qizi

Teacher

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13912924>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 01- Oktyabr 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 05- Oktyabr 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 10- Oktyabr 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

teacher, development, activity, personality-oriented technology, professional training.

ABSTRACT

This article examines developing student-centered teaching and learning at school. The personality of a teacher is a complex structural formation, representing a system of values, meanings of life and professional activity. It is relevant and significant to study the abilities of a teacher as a subject of his own professional activity, which involves the relationship and interdependence of qualitative changes in the personality of the teacher himself and in the personality of his students, taking them into account when assessing the professionalism of a teacher. A future teacher has his own set of personal and professionally important abilities and qualities that make up personal and professional potentials, which are prerequisites for his success in his work.

An important psychological problem is the study of the pedagogical abilities of the teacher of English, since teachers of literature have a positive influence on the formation of the personality of students, implementing moral and aesthetic education of schoolchildren. The determining factor in increasing the effectiveness of educational work at school is the high level of professional training of the teacher, which largely depends on the level of development of his pedagogical abilities, so it is important to determine the optimal conditions for their formation and development at all stages of training students - future teachers of English. Pedagogical abilities are closely related to general (mental) abilities, with character traits and emotionality of the teacher, as well as with special abilities, in particular, literary, linguistic. Special abilities are manifested in the activities of the teacher and serve pedagogical creativity only in the presence of pedagogical abilities and pedagogical focus. Pedagogical abilities are formed and developed in the process of training at school, special pedagogical educational institutions and in practical work with schoolchildren. Abilities are usually considered as individual psychological properties of the personality that contribute to the successful implementation of activities. Pedagogical abilities are defined as individual stable personality traits consisting of specific sensitivity to the object, means, conditions of pedagogical work and the creation of productive models for the formation of the desired personality traits of the student [3].

Speaking about pedagogical abilities as a specific sensitivity to various aspects of pedagogical activity, we mean that they are not an independent, isolated system in the

structure of the teacher's personality, but are manifested in all his mental processes - in the features of attention, perception, memory, thinking, speech, imagination, emotional states and direction. In addition, the higher the level of organization of the system of these qualities, the wider the opportunities for the individual in implementing self-realization and performing socially significant functions in the course of professional and pedagogical activity [4].

The modern development of society is characterized by innovative processes, the humanistic tendencies of which have led to an understanding of the need to develop a new educational paradigm aimed at the transition from the reproductive-informational model of education to a productive, humanistic one, orienting the pedagogical process towards the personal growth of future specialists. This approach increases the requirements for the personality of students, their ability to be responsible for their actions, the internal integrity and structure of the entire system of personal relationships (to themselves, others, the world as a whole) [1]. The organization of personality-oriented learning involves the development of pedagogical technologies with the aim of constantly enriching the student with creative experience, forming mechanisms of self-organization and self-realization of the individual. An important characteristic of the subject is the ability to reflect on their actions and their entire life. Education in the new paradigm requires a revision of the content and technology of teaching, a transition to a qualitatively new approach to the problem of relations between the subjects of the educational process. Personally oriented education of the humanistic type can be characterized as ensuring the development of the individual, support for its individuality, full satisfaction of its educational, spiritual, cultural, life needs and requests, providing freedom of choice of the content and ways of obtaining education, as well as ways of self-realization of the individual in the cultural and educational space. The personal component of this approach is in the construction of training taking into account the past experience of the student, his personal capabilities and characteristics, the integration of all socially valuable personality traits, a creative search for training and education options adequate to his capabilities and characteristics. "Learning is a change in the subject of activity, his transformation from someone who does not possess certain knowledge, skills and abilities into someone who has mastered them, i.e. "The activity of learning can be defined as the activity of self-change, self-development" [5].

In a pedagogical university, the process of cognition is built with the purpose of revealing and developing the personality of a student - a future teacher. Here there is a real opportunity to use scientific research as a means of implementing educational activities. Involving students in experimental work has a very large psychological effect. This helps students better understand the essence of innovative processes in the modern education system and consciously develop their own style of professional behavior. A pedagogical university combines the primacy of fundamental (psychological, pedagogical and subject) education with a focus on the realities and prospects of future professional activity. Personally oriented education does not deal with the formation of a personality with given properties, but creates conditions for its full manifestation and development.

The initial methodological premise of the concept of personality-oriented education is that it is initially developed as a pedagogical theory, i.e. personality development is considered as an activity for personality development. Personality, experience of performing personal functions (selectivity, reflection, meaning-determination, volitional self-regulation,

social responsibility, creativity, autonomy) constitute the specific content of education. Mastering personal experience also presupposes special teaching technologies, which are based on the creation of a situation of personality development - a set of pedagogical conditions that actualize the mechanisms of personal self-organization (by entering the space of problems that are significant for him), reflection and meaning-determination in relation to learning as the main sphere of life, assessment of one's achievements, setting individual educational goals, etc. The model of personality-oriented education presupposes the presence of a number of conditions, both internal and external, contributing to its effective implementation. External conditions:

1) individualization of training, which provides for the implementation by the student of an individual training program, focused on specific educational needs and learning goals and taking into account the experience, level of training, and individual psychological characteristics of the student;

2) contextuality of learning, which consists in the fact that learning, on the one hand, pursues specific, vitally important goals for the student, is focused on the fulfillment of social roles or personal development, on the other hand, it is built taking into account the subjective activity of the student and his spatial, temporal, professional, everyday factors, which implies strengthening the humanitarian component of the content of learning;

3) actualization of learning outcomes, meaning active, systematic application in practice of the knowledge, skills, abilities, and personal qualities acquired by the student;

4) stage-by-stage learning, which implies gradual, step-by-step formation of the pedagogical activity of students, which in turn requires correlation of the timing and volume of learning [2].

Internal conditions:

1) independence, which implies independent educational activity to develop pedagogical abilities. Independent activity is understood as the conscious implementation by students of the organization of the learning process, active participation in planning and evaluating the results of their educational activity;

2) awareness of learning, which means the student's awareness, understanding of all parameters of the learning process and their actions to organize it.

The main feature of psychological and pedagogical concepts of personality-oriented education is a purposeful and systematic study of the personality of each student, identification and recording of the dynamics of holistic development through the analysis of intellectual, activity, motivational and communicative spheres, as the main components in their relationship and dynamics. This allows us to identify the criteria and indicators of the formation of the student's personality in the learning process:

1) the motivational criterion includes the interests and needs of students in the development of pedagogical abilities;

2) the intellectual criterion - knowledge of the system and culture of pedagogical activity;

3) the activity criterion - skills and abilities, the ability to plan and implement independent educational activities, to develop abilities.

The personality-oriented system of training future English teachers reveals new content of the components of the methodological system and is seen in determining the

target, substantive and procedural characteristics of the training system, humanization of principles, goals, content, subject-subject relations, methods and forms of training, as well as organizational forms. For the formation and development of components of special pedagogical abilities, the following conditions are necessary: external, organizational, and internal, psychological. Internal, psychological conditions include students' awareness of the importance of special abilities for them as future English teachers, as well as an active, positive attitude to their development in themselves. External conditions are the appropriate organization of educational and upbringing work on the development of special pedagogical abilities in students during their studies at the university, the development and implementation of a program of a complex - a synthesis of a special course, a special seminar and a special practical course; cooperation with English language methodologists in organizing and conducting pedagogical practice; systematic nature of classes and control; collective self-development of abilities, etc.

The following requirements were imposed on the formative experiment:

- the system of tasks must be completed by each student, their completion must awaken in students a professional interest in psychological and pedagogical sciences, and maximally contribute to the preparation of the future teacher for independent work;
- the content and nature of the tasks must sufficiently fully reflect the structure of the master teacher's activity and contribute to the formation and development of special pedagogical abilities in students;
- the forms and methods of teaching must organically combine theoretical understanding of activity patterns and practical actions of students, contribute to the formation of correct pedagogical thinking and create conditions for managing the educational activities of students in the process of completing tasks.

As the conducted research has shown, teaching students according to a system of tasks reflecting the structure of the activity of a highly qualified teacher creates favorable conditions for managing the process of developing abilities. The process of forming and developing special pedagogical abilities and skills occurred in stages. Thus, the knowledge they received was updated and acquired practical significance. At the same time, they learn to analyze their activities and evaluate the degree of their mastery of special skills.

Thus, in modern education over the last decade of the educational paradigm, the knowledge-based approach to training specialists has been replaced by the recognition of the priorities of developing the competencies of the teacher's personality based on the technology of a personality-oriented approach. There was a need to change the educational environment in training specialists in higher education. The concept of modernizing the Uzbek education system defined the main goal of training: to prepare a teacher so that he could teach a child at school so that he could subsequently meet the urgent needs of society, production and the economy. Therefore, serious changes should also occur in the training of future teachers. A graduate of a pedagogical institute should come to school with a completely different view of the child, his education and his mission in the educational process. Successful resolution of the problems of modernization of education is possible under the condition of a fundamentally different, different from the traditional structuring of the content of professional education based on a competency-based approach and focus on such educational results as professional competencies

References:

1. Akhmetova T. (2022). Development of competencies in the personally-oriented professional training of a school teacher in a pedagogical university. Bulletin of the Russian State Pedagogical University named after A. I. Herzen, (63-2).
2. Imamatinov R. A. (2023). Development of pedagogical abilities in future teachers based on a personally-oriented approach. Scientific research in education, (3), 162-169.
3. Sattorov H. Competencies and competence-based approach in modern education. N. : Ilm-fan, 2024.
4. Kamilov I. K. Educational possibilities of practice-oriented teaching of students // Bulletin of science and education. No. 3. P. 113-119.
5. Yuldasheva N. A. Laws of a well-organized school. M-T.: Publishing House Novy Mir, 2023.

